

Environmental Harms Arising from
Warfare and Its Gendered Impacts:
An Extended Literature Review.

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Abstract

This dissertation explores the environmental impacts caused by warfare and examines the disproportionate impact of these harms on women. An interdisciplinary approach drawing on green criminology and feminist frameworks examines conflict-driven environmental damage and how it creates unique vulnerabilities for women and exacerbates existing gender inequalities. The dissertation identified critical links between militarism, environmental degradation and gendered vulnerabilities through a systematic literature review and thematic analysis of international case studies. The intersection of environmental justice and gender justice is evaluated, arguing that traditional criminological frameworks tend to overlook the impacts of warfare on marginalised populations and non-human species. This dissertation identifies a need for more inclusive and gendered approaches to post-conflict environmental recovery and policy development.

Contents Page

Acknowledgements	1
Abstract	2
Contents Page	3
Chapter 1: Introduction	6
1.1 Research Problem	6
1.2 Rationale	6
1.3 Theoretical and Disciplinary Context.....	6
1.4 Dissertation Aims and Objectives	6
1.5 Research Questions.....	7
Chapter 2: Methodology	8
2.1 Research Scope and Focus	8
2.2 Acknowledgement of Limitations.....	8
2.3 Reflexivity	8
2.4 Methods Used	9
2.5 Overview of Research Chapters	9
Chapter 3: Militarism Through a Criminological Lens	10
3.1 Introduction.....	10
3.2 Defining Militarism and Warfare	10
3.3 Criminological Perspectives of War	10
3.4 The Gendered Perspectives of War in Criminology.....	11
3.5 Conclusion	12
Chapter 4: Understanding Environmental Harm Through a Criminological Lens	13
4.1 Introduction.....	13
4.2 What is Green Criminology?.....	13
4.3 Environmental Crimes VS. Environmental Harms.....	14
4.4 The Treadmill of Production Theory.....	15
4.5 The Treadmill of Production Theory Applied to the United States Military.....	15
4.6 Conclusion	16
Chapter 5: Unintentional Environmental Impacts Caused by Militarism	17

5.1 Introduction.....	17
5.2 Environmental Neglect During Conflict	17
5.3 Indirect Environmental Impacts of Warfare	18
5.4 Unexploded Munitions	18
5.5 Habitat loss.....	18
5.6 Pollution Arising from Military Activities	19
5.7 Nuclear Weapons Testing.....	20
5.8 Conclusion	21
Chapter 6: Direct Environmental Destruction Caused by Militarism	22
6.1 Introduction.....	22
6.2 Intentional Environmental Harm in Warfare and How It’s Controlled	22
6.3 Exemplary Cases of Intentional Environmental Harm Caused by Militarism	23
6.3.1 The Use of Herbicides in Indochina	23
6.3.2 Detonation of the Kakhovka Dam.....	24
6.3.3 Militarisation of the South China Sea	24
6.4 Conclusion	25
Chapter 7: The Disproportionate Impact of Military-Driven Environmental Damage on Women.....	26
7.1 Introduction.....	26
7.2 Legal Recognition of the Intersectionality of Militarism, the Environment and Gender	26
7.3 The Unique Vulnerabilities of Conflict-Driven Environmental Degradation Faced by Women....	27
7.4 Women and Conflict-Induced Natural Disasters: The Kakhovka Dam	27
7.5 The Effects of Herbicides on Women’s Health: The Second Indochina War	28
7.6 Conclusion	28
Chapter 8: Conclusion.....	29
8.1 How can criminological frameworks help understand and address environmental harm arising from warfare and its gendered dimensions?	29
8.2 How is the health of the environment neglected during wartime, what are the unintentional and intentional ecological impacts of militarism?	29
8.3 How well do current laws and regulations protect the environment against military activities?29	
8.4 How are women disproportionately affected by conflict-related environmental harm?.....	30
8.5 Summary and a Connection of the Findings.....	30
8.6 Contextualising the Findings Considering Existing Literature	31
8.7 Critical Evaluation of the Methodology	31
8.7.1 What Worked?	31

8.7.2 Limitations	32
8.7.3 Future Improvements.....	32
8.7 Applicability: Policy and Practice Recommendations	32
8.8 Future Research Directions	33
References	34

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1 Research Problem

Humanity has been involved in conflict for thousands of years. As technology has advanced, so have the weapons and tools used by militaries (Jarose, 2024). These advancements have reshaped warfare and increased the likelihood of conflict (Huwart and Verdier, 2013), inevitably creating widespread environmental destruction (Jarose, 2024; Kotsis, 2024; Lynch et al., 2017; Lawrence et al., 2015; Westing, 2007). The survival of all life relies on the health of our planet. Warfare is destroying and polluting non-human species and ecosystems; it is, therefore, crucial for international law to recognise the severe damage that warfare causes (Jarose, 2024). The environmental damage that militarism is causing has a disproportionate impact on the health and survival of women - an issue that, to date, has been underexplored (Wonders and Danner, 2015).

1.2 Rationale

Militarism ultimately damages and discriminates against the natural environment and women. This problem needs to be addressed more adequately and reflected in practices and policies worldwide. This dissertation focuses on this research intersection to explore how criminological frameworks can advance our understanding of gendered environmental harm during warfare.

1.3 Theoretical and Disciplinary Context

This dissertation expands on existing literature, providing an interdisciplinary insight by connecting green criminology, gender studies, military studies, environmental science, and international law. The anthropocentric bias within traditional criminology and international legal norms is challenged by ecofeminist studies and green criminological frameworks. Arguing that ecological destruction is a humanitarian issue that disproportionately impacts women and should be recognised as a crime in its own right.

1.4 Dissertation Aims and Objectives

This dissertation aims to uncover different forms of ecological harm caused by militarism and how gendered vulnerabilities shape their effects. It will examine:

- Weak and limited legal protections for non-human species and ecosystems

- The intersectionality between gender, militarism and the environment.
- Criminological frameworks surrounding war, green criminology, and ecofeminism will be analysed.

1.5 Research Questions

1. How can criminological frameworks help understand and address environmental harm arising from warfare, and its gendered dimensions?
2. How is the health of the environment neglected during wartime, what are the unintentional and intentional ecological impacts of militarism?
3. How well do current laws and regulations protect the environment against military activities?
4. How are women disproportionately affected by conflict-related environmental harm?

Chapter 2: Methodology

2.1 Research Scope and Focus

This dissertation focuses on environmental harms linked to militarism from 1962 onward, emphasising case studies such as the Second Indochina War, the conflict in Ukraine, and military land reclamation in the South China Sea. It uses secondary research methods to analyse documented instances of ecological destruction and gender-based vulnerability, highlighting the long-term, borderless impacts of militarism on global ecosystems and marginalised populations.

2.2 Acknowledgement of Limitations

Due to practical, ethical, legal, and safety constraints, primary research was not possible. Military and war-related research often requires access permissions and presents risks that reach beyond the scope of an undergraduate dissertation. Conducting fieldwork in an area affected by war would pose significant ethical and security concerns, as it could endanger the researcher and potential participants. There is peer-reviewed literature, government reports, and NGO assessments that already exist on the environmental consequences of war, making secondary research a more practical approach. The chosen case studies have been extensively documented, allowing strong analysis without the need for new data collection.

2.3 Reflexivity

This research recognises that while environmental and social harms exist independently of our perceptions, social, cultural and political contexts shape our understanding of them. This is relevant considering the lack of recognition of gendered and ecological harms within legal and traditional criminological frameworks. This project acknowledges that knowledge about environmental harm and gendered experiences are socially constructed, and can be affected by dominant ideologies, such as militarism, patriarchy and anthropocentrism. Therefore, the research critically engages with literature to interpret the meanings and absences within existing laws. The researcher's decision to focus on gendered and ecological issues and to draw from ecofeminist and green criminological literature reflects a deliberate effort to highlight subjects often excluded from traditional literature and legal systems.

2.4 Methods Used

This research adopted the Finch and Fafinski (2019) (Appendix 1) method as a structured approach to ensure accurate and relevant analysis, promoting critical evaluation when comparing existing literature. A comprehensive database search was conducted using JSTOR, Google Scholar, UWE Library, and Sage Journals, which provided credible, peer-reviewed research. The search was refined using keywords such as “militarism”, “ecosystems”, “gender”, and “biodiversity loss”, along with alternative spellings and phrasings, such as “militarization”. Boolean operators, for example, “militarism AND ecocide”, were applied to enhance search precision. Additionally, the research focused on data from 1962 onwards, to ensure the inclusion of the Second Indochina War. However, literature discussing World War II was briefly included for contextual relevance. To ensure the reliability and relevance of the selected literature, the Open University’s PROMPT checklist was applied (Smith, 2020) (Appendix 2). Once sufficient literature was collected, a thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke’s (2017) framework was conducted to identify recurring themes.

2.5 Overview of Research Chapters

Ecofeminist and gendered perspectives are examined within Chapters 1 and 5. Chapter 1 aims to introduce the reader to definitions of militarism and warfare relevant to this dissertation and frames the issue within criminology, including gendered and ecofeminist theories. The masculinisation of the military is analysed using criminological and ecofeminist studies. Chapters 2 to 4 use green criminological literature to assess the lack of recognition of environmental harms within international laws and the anthropocentric nature of existing laws. Chapter 2 outlines green criminology and the Treadmill of Production Theory, which is applied to the United States military-industrial complex. Chapter 3 discusses indirect and unintentional environmental harms caused by military activities, emphasising the need for stronger environmental legal protections. Chapter 4 expands on Chapter 3 by analysing intentional ecological destruction. Three case studies uncover how the environment has been targeted during wartime and the environmental and humanitarian consequences of these actions. Chapter 5 brings the reader back to ecofeminist literature, discussing the intersectionality of gender and conflict-driven ecological harms. The absence of legal recognition for this intersectionality is assessed. The unique vulnerabilities that women experience during natural disasters and environmental destruction are analysed using examples from the case studies in Chapter 4.

Chapter 3: Militarism Through a Criminological Lens

3.1 Introduction

This chapter explores the concepts of warfare and militarism, defining key terms and examining how criminologists have approached the study of war. It discusses the limited criminological research on militarism, highlighting challenges such as data accessibility and the discipline's positivist foundations. The chapter also analyses the role of capitalism in sustaining military presence from a criminological perspective. Finally, a gendered focus is applied to militarism, incorporating ecofeminist insights from scholars like Wonders and Danner (2015) and examining how militarism is shaped by masculinity.

3.2 Defining Militarism and Warfare

There is no consensus on how best to define militarism and warfare (Benvenuti, 2009; Harper, 2001; Rumpf, 1938; Eagleton, 1932). Cambridge Dictionary (2019) defines militarism as "the belief that it is necessary to have strong armed forces and that they should be used in order to win political or economic advantages". The Oxford English Dictionary (2025) defines warfare as "the action of waging war; armed conflict. Also in early use: military life or service". In this dissertation, militarism and warfare refer to military practices and activities that prepare militaries and states for war and the actions and tools used during wartime.

3.3 Criminological Perspectives of War

War perpetuates criminal acts (such as homicide, sexual violence, and destruction of property), victimisation and human rights violations on a much larger scale than domestic levels of crime. Despite this, criminologists have paid little attention to the study of war (DiPietro, 2016; Walklate and McGarry, 2015; Jamieson, 2017). Some criminologists suggest that struggles in accessing conflict zones and collecting data in areas that have been devastated have led to a lack of research within criminology, especially when it comes to studying genocide (DiPietro, 2016; Hagan and Raymond-Richmond, 2008). Walklate and McGarry (2015) argue that criminology's reluctance to study war and state-sponsored violence stems from its positivist roots, which have kept the discipline focused on crime and criminal justice within state institutions. Because criminologists have traditionally worked alongside these institutions, they may be hesitant to be critical of the state's actions (DiPietro, 2016; Walklate and McGarry, 2015). Bonger (1916) (cited in Walklate and McGarry, 2015: p. 7) expresses the influence of

capitalism on the persistence and growth of militarism, explaining that militarism serves as a way for hegemonic capitalist societies to control domestic populations, protect sovereign borders and exploit foreign territory for capital gain. Moreover, it has been discussed that militaries must stay in this growth continuum to preserve their existence: “Nothing is more demoralising to an army or to a military state than peace” (Walklate and McGarry, 2015: p. 7).

Whilst traditional criminology lacks the inclusion of war within its frameworks, ecofeminism, the intersectional study of feminism and ecology (Puleo, 2017), and green criminological perspectives address environmental harms caused by militarism during wartime and peacetime as an eco-crime (Lynch et al., 2017; O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016; Stretsky et al., 2014). Many green criminologists and ecofeminists highlight that environmental harms arising from military activities are perpetuated and ignored by the powerful, such as states; in turn, vulnerable, civilian populations experience the worst consequences (O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Traditional criminological literature addressing militarism is mostly outdated, missing the importance of current conflicts such as the Russian invasion of Ukraine and the Israeli attacks on Gaza. Awareness of gendered and ecological issues has increased in recent years; these have not been captured in past criminological frameworks surrounding warfare.

3.4 The Gendered Perspectives of War in Criminology

Militarism has always been a male-dominated field. Despite women now being allowed to join the military in most countries, they still experience barriers deeply rooted in negative attitudes from their male peers who feel as though combat should remain a male profession (Higate and Hopton, 2004; Winslow and Dunn, 2001). “Militarism has tended to work against the interests of women, often in ways that directly benefit men” (Higate and Hopton, 2004: p. 437). Militarism promotes hegemonically masculine traits such as strength, stoicism, risk-taking, violence, aggression and domination (Jamieson, 2017; Higate and Hopton, 2004). Some scholars refer to military training as a process of masculinisation (Jamieson, 2017; Connell, 1995). Some scholars believe the performance of hegemonic masculinities - in this case, traits associated with soldiering- is deeply linked to climate change and that greater value is placed on these male-dominated fields (Wonders and Danner, 2015; True, 2012; Sollund et al., 2015). The performance and idolisation of hegemonic masculinities have led to a narrow societal focus on economic growth and profit, which is damaging our planet and people globally (Wonders and Danner, 2015; True, 2012). Some ecofeminists view the planet as a reflection of femininity that is being exploited by patriarchy in the same way women have been (Wonders and Danner, 2015).

Rape is often used as a weapon in war. Brownmiller (1975) believes that rape is an expression of aggression and dominance, predominantly to keep women in a state of fear and not an act of sexual desire. Often in wartime, men will rape other men to feminise, homosexualise, and dehumanise their opponents, as femininity is viewed as a weakness (Jamieson, 2017).

3.5 Conclusion

This chapter provided definitions of warfare and militarism that are relevant to this paper. It examined warfare and militarism through a criminological lens, focusing on the discipline's reluctance to study war due to methodological limitations, positivist traditions and ties to state institutions. It examined capitalism's role in sustaining militarism for capital and economic gain and the military's need for continuous growth. It also explored how capitalism and military structures reinforce hegemonic masculinity, marginalising women. Ecofeminist perspectives further linked militarism to environmental and social harm.

Chapter 4: Understanding Environmental Harm Through a Criminological Lens

4.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the reader to the field of green criminology, exploring its origins and development as an area of study within criminology. The perspectives of key scholars such as Michael Lynch, Rob White, and Paul Stretsky will be explored to gain an understanding of green criminology. It will investigate the reasons why green scholars expanded their focus beyond legally defined environmental crimes to include environmental harms, highlighting the importance of addressing issues that may not be captured by existing legal frameworks. Finally, the Treadmill of Production theory (Schnaiberg, 1980; Stretsky et al., 2014; Lynch et al., 2017) will be analysed and applied to the United States military-industrial complex to give a deeper understanding of the theory's implications and its relevance to environmental and criminological studies.

4.2 What is Green Criminology?

Michael Lynch was the first to introduce green criminology in the 1990s (Lynch 1990; Frank and Lynch 1992). There is no clear definition of what constitutes green criminology, with Eman, Mesko, and Fields (2009, p. 577) suggesting that “the lack of an agreed definition of green criminology presents an additional problem in the field of research surrounding environmental criminality.” Lynch et al. (2017, p. 10) work around this by focusing on societies' economic and political structures, which produce environmental destruction and ecological disorganisation. Green criminology helps us to view crime from an ecocentric perspective, whilst traditional criminology commonly follows an anthropocentric ideology which focuses on conventional crimes against people and property (Lea and Young, 1984). Green criminology gives us an ecological perception of crimes and harms (Nurse, 2016). The criminal justice system was created to deal with behaviour that is prohibited by the law (Situ and Emmons, 2000), but neglects crimes and harms that involve non-traditional victims / non-human species (Nurse, 2015). Green criminology opens us up to the idea that non-human species, ecosystems, and the biosphere can also be victims of human activities (Brisman and South, 2018: p.1). Rob White (2008, p. 50) suggests that “green criminology emphasises environmental justice, with a special focus on human rights and social equity; and ecological justice, with a special focus on the biosphere generally and the rights of non-human as well as human.” Environmental harm may be considered socially acceptable

and legal, for example, the exploitation of natural resources by corporations and states (Walters et al., 2013; Stallworthy, 2008). The short-term impact of environmental harm isn't always obvious. However, it can lead to the long-term deterioration of our ecosystems, which in turn negatively impacts human health, the economy and our survival (Nurse, 2015; Hall, 2013). Environmental harm can be a complex concept to understand due to the many causes which can result in direct, indirect, immediate and cumulative harm (Heckenberg, 2010; Lin, 2006).

4.3 Environmental Crimes VS. Environmental Harms

Generally, green criminology studies environmental crimes. However, environmental harms that are not currently illegal are also relevant to the field (White, 2014). Some scholars limit their understanding of green crimes and harms to specific acts that violate the law or environmental protection statutes (Situ and Emmons, 2000). This definition is easier understood as it is recognised by law enforcement (Lynch et al., 2017). Environmental crimes include “illegal dumping of toxic waste, the illegal transfer of hazardous materials (e.g. ozone-depleting substances), the illegal traffic in radioactive or nuclear substances, the illegal trade in flora and fauna, and illegal fishing and logging” (White and Heckenberg, 2014: p. 11). Environmental crimes aren't always integrated into our criminal justice system or dealt with by criminal justice agencies like the police; they often become the responsibility of separate environmental departments such as the UK Environmental Agency (Nurse, 2015). Carrabine et al. (2004) (cited in White and Heckenberg, 2014: p. 14) categorise environmental crimes as primary and secondary crimes: primary crimes “result directly from the destruction and degradation of the Earth's resources, through human actions”; secondary crimes are “crimes arising out of the flouting of rules that seek to regulate environmental disasters”. The lack of effective regulation and enforcement of environmental laws is the main cause of environmental crime (Situ and Emmons, 2000). These laws still seem to be undervalued compared to laws that prosecute traditional criminal behaviour or protect human victims directly (White and Heckenberg, 2014). Considering environmental harm alongside crimes within green criminology is vital because environmental laws are not effective enough. For example, the governing of toxic waste and pollution is difficult to impose when companies can legally cause ecological destruction through pollution if they have a pollution permit (Lynch et al., 2017). This is why green criminology quickly expanded its considerations to focus on environmental harms that are not necessarily illegal (Frank and Lynch, 1992). Lynch et al. (2017: p. 3) describe environmental harm as “an act that regardless of its legality causes significant identifiable harm to ecological systems.” “Green criminology therefore provides an umbrella under which to theorise and critique both illegal environmental harms [...] and legal environmental harms [...] how harm is conceptualised is thus partly

shaped by how the legal-illegal divide is constructed within specific research and analysis.” (White and Heckenberg, 2014: p. 13).

4.4 The Treadmill of Production Theory

Lynch et al. (2017) and Stretsky et al. (2014) adapted Schnaiberg’s (1980) Treadmill of Production (ToP) theory. This theory expresses how capitalist societies are trapped in a cycle of pursuing profit through relentless growth in production; we strive for economic expansion, which results in the exploitation of natural resources beyond their capacity and increases waste and pollution. The ToP can be understood using concepts from physics; thermodynamics tells us that “energy cannot be created or destroyed, only transformed”, and the law of entropy, “as energy is transformed in production; it takes on less organised forms” (Lynch et al., 2017). As we use extracted materials from our environment for other means, such as fuel, the material is changed from an organised, stored energy into a disorganised energy which is dispersed into our environment (Lynch et al., 2017). We have a limited amount of stored energy and materials on Earth. As consumption increases, we have less stored energy and more pollution (Lynch et al., 2017). This theory is applied to capitalism’s role in militarism and its effects on the environment. Stretsky et al. (2014) recognise the severe ecological impact of militarism, however, international law does not treat environmental destruction as a crime of war or hold militaries and states accountable for the harm they cause.

4.5 The Treadmill of Production Theory Applied to the United States Military

The military-industrial complex is a system in which governments, corporations and the military work together to maintain security and engage in conflict, often driven by economic gain and the pursuit of geopolitical power. It is one of the world’s largest polluters; however, its emissions are rarely regulated (Belcher, 2022). The US military was found to be “consuming more liquid fuels and emitting more CO₂e (carbon dioxide equivalent) than most [entire] countries.” (Lancaster University, 2019). The US is exempt from reporting military emissions after withdrawing from the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, an international agreement designed by the United Nations to reduce greenhouse gases (Lewis, 2021). This exemption allows military operations to continue polluting without accountability for their actions, reflecting the ToP’s tendency to prioritise economic and security interests over environmental concerns. Despite the Pentagon in the US recognising climate change as a threat to national security, its response is to expand military budgets to adapt to climate-related risks, rather than addressing its root causes and preventing these future disasters (Belcher, 2022). The military complex seeks continuous expansion, calling for more resources, energy and funding to sustain itself. This creates a

cycle of increased production, fossil fuel consumption and pollution, all leading to climate change (Belcher, 2022). “Using stored energy [(fossil fuels, coal, etc.)] for work increases the temperature of the system, which affects climate change” (Lynch et al., 2017).

4.6 Conclusion

Green criminology provides an important framework for understanding the intersectionality of environmental issues and criminology. By expanding traditional criminology to include environmental harms- both legal and illegal - green criminology challenges us to reconsider the concept of victimisation and the responsibilities of the criminal justice system. By exploring the Treadmill of Production, we gain an understanding of the systemic forces that lead to ecological destruction and the role of powerful institutions like the military-industrial complex in perpetuating environmental harm. This broader perspective not only deepens our understanding of crime and justice but also calls for effective environmental protections and accountability measures to safeguard the planet, humans and non-human species.

Chapter 5: Unintentional Environmental Impacts Caused by Militarism

5.1 Introduction

This chapter addresses the weak protections of non-human species and how they are further neglected during wartime, exploring which aspects of conflict cause difficult conditions for environmental protection. There will be a brief explanation with examples of the positive environmental aspects of war. The unintentional negative environmental consequences will be examined to express how positive effects are soon hugely outweighed, going into detail about unexploded munitions, habitat loss, pollution arising from military activities, and nuclear weapons testing.

5.2 Environmental Neglect During Conflict

Non-human species lack their own rights. Their rights solely depend on the status given to them by humans; thus, if they are labelled as human property (e.g. pets, livestock and private land), they experience better protection (Nurse, 2016). Most countries have laws protecting animal welfare and wildlife, which usually have human interests at the heart of them (Nurse, 2016). Article 55 of the 1977 Geneva Conventions states, “Care shall be taken in warfare to protect the natural environment against widespread, long-term and severe damage.” (Jarose, 2024). However, as Situ and Emmons (2000) emphasise, laws protecting non-human species are not enforced effectively and are often overlooked. “We need a jurisprudence that would provide for the legal rights of geological and biological as well as human components of the Earth community. A legal system exclusively for humans is not realistic” (Berry, cited in Higgins et al., 2013). Environmental concerns become an even lower priority during wartime and political unrest; this is made more complicated when monitoring infrastructures are destroyed and experts must flee their countries (Van der Vet, 2024; Hanson et al., 2009). The ability to collect reliable data on conflict pollution and harm caused to the environment is diminished when areas of control are split by territorial disputes, particularly when that data is used as a tool to blame or spread misinformation (Van der Vet, 2024). The scale of damage that warfare inflicts on ecosystems depends on the strategies and weapons used, the sensitivity and resilience of the ecosystem and the amount of time the impacts were being imposed (Lawrence et al., 2015; Dudley et al., 2002; Westing, 1971). Some impacts of conflict on our environment are not visible and can be slow to emerge, meaning that they can be missed in post-conflict assessments (Van der Vet, 2024; Nixon, 2011).

5.3 Indirect Environmental Impacts of Warfare

Some scholars argue that war may reduce everyday human activities that produce environmental harm, leading to an increase in biodiversity, particularly in zones that the military has designated off-limits (Lawrence et al., 2015; Reuveny et al., 2010; Dudley et al., 2002; Martin and Szuter, 1999). For example, during World War II fish stocks flourished in the Atlantic Ocean; certain species that were overexploited for consumption were protected by the threat of naval or aerial strikes (Lawrence et al., 2015; Reuveny et al., 2010; Beare et al., 2010). Sunken ships, mainly accumulating in WWII, now serve as artificial reefs, becoming habitats for aquatic life (Lawrence et al., 2015; Hynes et al., 2004). Some carnivorous species, such as Bengal tigers and leopards can benefit from ground conflict by feeding on casualties who are left behind (Lawrence et al., 2015; Westing, 1980). However, Dudley et al. (2002) note that the negative effects of warfare on the environment significantly outweigh the benefits.

5.4 Unexploded Munitions

Landmines and still explosive 'duds' present a long-lasting danger to wildlife and humans (Lawrence et al., 2015; Westing, 1996). "The vast majority of all landmines used in warfare are, in fact, not set off by the combatants at which they are directed, and most of them remain ready to explode for many decades into the future" (Westing, 1996: p. 283). Around 10% of high-explosive munitions do not explode as intended when released, labelled as 'duds'; about 50% of duds remain ready to explode when disrupted by human or animal activities (Westing, 1996). According to the charity organisation Mines Advisory Group (MAG), 13 people are killed or injured every day by unexploded landmines and bombs (MAG, 2025). In 2020, MAG destroyed 115,627 landmines and unexploded bombs worldwide (MAG, 2025), just a small portion of what remains. Westing (1996) claims there are about 65 million functional landmines and even more still-explosive duds globally. Rural areas that were once used as battlefields are important to human populations to carry out routine activities such as agriculture, horticulture and hunting, but present a high risk of disrupting explosives (MAG, 2025; Westing, 1996). Contaminated land prevents poorer communities from rebuilding after returning to their native lands post-conflict, such as villagers in Eastern Angola, one of the most heavily mined countries in the world, who are still returning home after 40 years of conflict and being displaced in countries like the Democratic Republic of Congo and Zambia (MAG, 2025).

5.5 Habitat loss

Ground conflict usually takes place in remote locations, which tend to be hotspots for wildlife (Lawrence et al., 2015; Hanson et al., 2009). The weapons used in ground conflict pose a threat to the structure of ecosystems, leaving behind craters, shrapnel, and contamination (Lawrence et al., 2015; Westing,

1980). Deforestation can arise because of the use of modern weapons and combat; however, it can also be an indirect consequence of refugees using wood for fuel and shelter when they are displaced by conflict (O'Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Deforestation and habitat destruction negatively impact biodiversity, ecosystems, and disease dynamics (Kotsis, 2024). This creates challenging conditions for the survival of native species and affects their interactions, which can lead to species extinction (Kotsis, 2024; O'Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Deforestation can cause droughts and desertification (O'Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Vegetation loss contributes to levels of CO₂ in our atmosphere, speeding up climate change (Kotsis, 2024).

Habitat degradation, population decline, and species extinction can also be caused by noise pollution from aircrafts and naval sonars (Lawrence et al., 2015; Mancini et al., 1998). Animals with sensitive auditory systems experience effects such as auditory masking (inability to identify noises from prey, predators and mates), eardrum ruptures, changes to hearing abilities, and beach stranding, which can all change natural behaviours and dynamics, having negative effects on their habitat (Lawrence et al., 2015; Mancini et al., 1998).

5.6 Pollution Arising from Military Activities

Militaries produce massive amounts of greenhouse gases during peacetime, and their consumption of fossil fuels increases during conflict, adding huge amounts of ozone-depleting pollutants to our atmosphere (O'Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Military infrastructure and equipment maintenance, manufacturing, and employment of weaponry and ammunition generate hazardous substances: heavy metals, solvents, corrosives, paints, fuel, oil and explosives (Kotsis, 2024; Lawrence et al., 2015). Prominent pollutants include lead, copper, and depleted uranium, which can contaminate and be transported substantial distances by/into soil, water, or as gaseous emissions (Kotsis, 2024; Edwards, 2002). These pollutants can be ingested or inhaled by animals and humans and have been proven to have negative consequences on neurological, cardiovascular, and reproductive systems (Kotsis, 2024; Edwards, 2002). Whole communities of wildlife are negatively affected by military pollution (Lawrence et al., 2015; Edwards, 2002). Pollutants can change ecosystems drastically when soil is polluted, relationships between predator and prey, soil food webs and vegetation are impacted (Edwards, 2002). For example, fuel spills, aircraft maintenance, and improper storage of hazardous waste by the Otis Air Base and the Norton Air Force Base in the United States have led to fuel contamination of groundwater and hazardous waste contamination in the environment (Lawrence et al., 2015).

Conflict pollution accumulates in various forms. Van der Vet's (2024) study focuses on the region of Donbas in Eastern Ukraine from 2014 to 2022, Europe's most heavily industrialised region. Ukraine is home to around 4500 hazardous mining, metallurgical, and chemical enterprises, all of which are at the front line of the conflict between Russia (Van der Vet, 2024). Ukraine had an effective environmental monitoring system in place before the conflict began; however, since Russia took over Donbas, environmental protection has collapsed (Van der Vet, 2024). The pumping of mines and supply chains of high-grade coal has been disrupted; mines that aren't being pumped now pose the risk of polluting water supplies, and industries were forced to switch to lower-grade, more polluting coals (Van der Vet, 2024; OSCE, 2017; Denisov and Averin, 2017). Tailing Storage Facilities (TSFs) store liquid and sludge waste from industrial sites and mines; in 2019, Ukraine had 465 TSFs storing over 6 billion tons of toxic waste (Van der Vet, 2024; OSCE, 2017). Toxic spills caused by the conflict could lead to a domino effect of pollution that will reach beyond Ukraine's borders, potentially spreading across the Black Sea region (Van der Vet, 2024; OSCE, 2017).

5.7 Nuclear Weapons Testing

According to Yang et al. (2003) (cited in Lawrence et al., 2015), there have been more than 2000 nuclear weapons tests around the world since the late 1990s. Lawrence et al. (2015) describe the effects of the three elements of nuclear explosions: thermal emissions, kinetic energy, and nuclear radiation. Thermal emissions from nuclear blasts can reach temperatures of around 3000 degrees Celsius at the epicentre of the blast; any life within this vicinity will be incinerated (Lawrence et al., 2015; Brode, 1968). Further from this epicentre, vegetation is burnt and defoliated (Lawrence et al., 2015; Shields and Wells, 1962), and any animals nearby will experience burns on the skin and retinas leading to infections which can be fatal (Lawrence et al., 2015; Shields and Wells, 1962; Oughterson and Warren, 1956; Brooks et al., 1952). Kinetic energy from the blast can uproot vegetation (Lawrence et al., 2015; Shields and Wells, 1962) and can injure and kill animals via the kinetic energy or from debris and shrapnel carried by the blast (Lawrence et al., 2015). Sea life can also be affected by a nuclear blast's kinetic energy; some fish have sensitive gas-filled swim bladders, which are easily ruptured. Nuclear blasts lead to large die-offs of fish populations (Lawrence et al., 2015). Nuclear radiation causes poisoning in humans and animals, destroying cells and creating a high risk of developing diseases (Lawrence et al., 2015; Mole, 1958). Plants can also suffer from tissue damage, often resulting in death (Lawrence et al., 2015; Sparrow and Woodwell, 1962). Nuclear testing creates widespread, long-term, and severe environmental damage, aligning with Article 55 of the 1977 Geneva Conventions, yet these activities do not face legal repercussions (Jarose, 2024).

5.8 Conclusion

Conflict removes the ability to monitor ecological damage by breaking down the already limited environmental governance. Militarism has far-reaching and often irreversible effects on the environment, impacting ecosystems, wildlife, and humans. The destruction of habitats and pollution from military activities during and outside of wartime contribute to long-term ecological degradation. Although temporary environmental gains may occur during conflict due to reduced human presence and useful remnants of war, these are outweighed by the extensive damage inflicted on natural systems.

Chapter 6: Direct Environmental Destruction Caused by Militarism

6.1 Introduction

Environmental destruction has been used as a war tactic; armed forces may destroy their environment or their oppositions for strategic gain or to cause widespread devastation (O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016; Reuveny et al., 2010). This chapter begins by exploring legislation that protects against environmental warfare and how they aren’t particularly effective in their aims. Next, the chapter goes on to explore different case studies, starting with the use of herbicides in the Second Indochina War and how this kick-started studies of Ecocide. A case study of the detonation of the Kakhovka dam in Ukraine and the unbiased borderless-ness of environmental damage. Finally, the chapter will discuss the militarisation of the South China Sea to give insight into how states can destroy their own environment to gain strategic control.

6.2 Intentional Environmental Harm in Warfare and How It’s Controlled

“The protection of the natural environment from further reckless destruction is a priority for all humanity. Therefore, one might assume that environmental warfare – “warfare in which the environment is manipulated for hostile military purposes” – would be completely prohibited.” (Jarose, 2024: p. 473; Westing 1985). The 1976 Convention on the Prohibition of Military or Any Other Hostile Use of Environmental Modification Techniques (ENMOD) seeks to prevent the deliberate manipulation of the Earth’s natural processes, such as manipulating tsunamis and earthquakes, using scientific techniques that trigger a natural disaster (Jarose, 2024; O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016; United Nations, 1976). ENMOD is problematic because man-made natural disasters do not exist (Jarose, 2024). Current, conventional warfare tactics don’t have the technological capabilities to weaponise the environment, but they do create huge amounts of environmental damage (O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016). The widespread use of herbicides may go against ENMOD: “Low-technology methods of damaging or otherwise changing the environment may qualify as environmental modification techniques under Article II of ENMOD” (Jarose, 2024: p. 472). This only applies if the effects have widespread, long-lasting, or severe effects, a high threshold to achieve before effective protections and actions are taken seriously (Jarose, 2024; O’Sullivan and Walters, 2016). Most environmental protection during wartime depends on whether the natural environment is considered a ‘civilian object’, due to

the anthropocentric nature of these rules, the natural environment will only be protected if it has a significant impact on human populations (Jarose, 2024). These rules only protect against military action which is intended or expected to cause devastating environmental damage. However, not all states believe these rules represent international law, such as the United States (Jarose, 2024).

6.3 Exemplary Cases of Intentional Environmental Harm Caused by Militarism

6.3.1 The Use of Herbicides in Indochina

The term Ecocide emerged in the aftermath of the Second Indochina War, during which the environment was targeted as a military strategy by the United States (Zeirler, 2011; Falk, 1973). Higgins (2012: p. 3) defines Ecocide as “the extensive damage, destruction to or loss of ecosystems of a given territory, whether by human agency or other causes, to such an extent that peaceful enjoyment by the inhabitants of that territory has been severely diminished.” In 2010, Polly Higgins proposed to the United Nations Law Commission that Ecocide should be the 5th Crime Against Peace in the Rome Statute, “Nations will be legally bound to act before mass damage, destruction or ecosystem collapse occurs and the law will impute a legal duty of care on all nations to provide assistance to those countries that are at risk of or are suffering from ecosystem collapse as a result of rising sea-levels or catastrophic events such as tsunamis and floods” (Higgins et al., 2013). This determines environmental damage as a crime of strict liability, whether committed during war or outside of war. Ten countries have included Ecocide in their criminal penal systems, although none of them have established a test of intent (Higgins et al., 2013).

The 1925 Geneva Protocol prohibits the use of chemical and biological weapons in warfare (United Nations, 1925). However, the United States did not ratify the Protocol until 1975, years after deploying approximately 77 million litres of chemical defoliants, mainly in Vietnam, between 1962 and 1971 (Cohen, 2024; Lawrence et al., 2015; Zeirler, 2011; Stellman et al., 2003; Falk, 1973; Johnstone, 1971). These chemical defoliants contained highly toxic dioxins, causing widespread environmental devastation and severe public health consequences, including congenital disabilities and increased cancer rates, which we are still seeing the effects of to this day (Truong and Dinh, 2021; Westing, 2012; Zeirler, 2011). The defoliants resulted in immediate vegetation mortality, as well as the deaths of many mammals (Lawrence et al., 2015). Soil degradation in heavily sprayed regions has rendered regrowth and agricultural productivity almost impossible, and the contamination of vital water sources continues to pose a threat to both ecological and human health (Wards and Burns, 2017; Lawrence et al., 2015).

Surveys carried out to compare unimpacted habitats with areas sprayed with herbicides showed remarkably less species diversity in the affected areas (Lawrence et al., 2015; Westing, 1989). However, limited environmental monitoring before the war made it difficult to determine the extent of the damage, as there was no data to compare with (Lawrence et al., 2015). Despite the scale of these environmental harms, Truong and Dinh (2021) highlight a critical gap in research on the ecological consequences of herbicidal warfare in the Second Indochina War. They argue that existing studies focus predominantly on the effects on local populations and military veterans, reflecting the anthropocentric bias in conflict studies.

6.3.2 Detonation of the Kakhovka Dam

The Kakhovka dam was detonated by Russian forces in 2023; the environmental harm caused by this reaches beyond Ukrainian borders (Van der Vet, 2024). Floods caused by the detonation reached densely populated areas, and industrial and agricultural waste polluted the Black Sea (Babin et al., 2023; Lawrence et al., 2015). Freshwater that was once contained by the dam has diluted the saline content within the Black Sea, fish and wildlife populations above and below the dam suffered abrasion, habitat loss and suffocation (Babin et al., 2023; Lawrence et al., 2015). Scientists in Ukraine have reported that four areas will suffer from a scarcity of drinking water due to the loss of reservoirs which were destroyed, as well as contamination of water supplies from hundreds of tons of engine oil released from mechanical equipment into the Dnipro River, and toxic substances and pathogens from the bottom of the reservoir will contaminate groundwater (Prokip, 2023). Forty-eight protected sites established by the Nature Reserves Fund face devastation (Prokip, 2023).

The Black Sea is extremely important to surrounding countries such as Bulgaria, Romania, and Turkey (Babin et al., 2023). These countries rely on the Black Sea for tourism, trade, travel, and industrial and energy development (Pahwa, 2023; Babin et al., 2023). The pollution caused by the destruction of the Kakhovka dam has had negative consequences for these countries, reflecting the borderless-ness of environmental harm (Beck, 2006). Arguably, the destruction of a dam with the knowledge of consequential widespread flooding and environmental damage goes against ENMOD and Article 55 of the 1977 Geneva Conventions (Jarose, 2024).

6.3.3 Militarisation of the South China Sea

From 2013 to 2015, China used land reclamation projects to convert 3,000 acres over seven coral reefs in the Spratly Islands (Southerland, 2016) into artificial islands for military bases, runways to host fighter jets, artillery units and naval ports (Marshall, 2016: pp.57-58). China competes for territory against

countries such as the Philippines, which are diplomatically linked to the USA. These land reclamation projects helped them to gain geopolitical power over the South China Sea (Marshall, 2016). However, Marshall (2016: p. 58) quotes US Defence Secretary Ash Carter, who said, "Turning an underwater rock into an airfield simply does not afford the rights of sovereignty or permit restrictions on international air or maritime transit." The Treadmill of Production theory is relevant to this case study; natural environments were exploited to gain strategic and economic control. (Lynch et al., 2017; Stretsky et al., 2014; Schnaiberg, 1980). The Spratly Islands were important to the ecology of the area, and much biodiversity has been lost due to the dredging that took place in this short period (Southerland, 2016). Coral reefs are extremely important to the biodiversity of the ocean, they are home to at least a quarter of the world's marine life, they protect shorelines from floods, they convert carbon dioxide into oxygen, and they filter toxins and contaminants out of the ocean (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 2024). Destruction of these reefs has had negative impacts on fisheries in the South China Sea, pushing local fishing boats further afield, creating tensions between other claimant countries (Southerland, 2016). China's destruction of reefs for military activities aligns with state-led economic expansion, increasing their control over sea lanes, which are crucial for global trade (Marshall, 2016: pp.57-58).

6.4 Conclusion

Direct environmental destruction in warfare is a damaging strategy which inflicts severe and lasting consequences on ecosystems and human populations. Despite international agreements like ENMOD, legal protections remain weak, often failing to prevent deliberate environmental harm due to anthropocentric biases and a lack of global enforcement. This chapter has examined how militaries intentionally target or manipulate the environment for strategic gain. Case studies on herbicidal warfare in the Second Indochina War, the deliberate destruction of the Kakhovka dam, and the militarisation of the Spratly Islands demonstrate the extent to which military operations knowingly degrade ecosystems. Deforestation, biodiversity loss, water contamination, and habitat destruction all show us how warfare weaponises the environment itself. Despite the clear and deliberate nature of these harms, accountability remains scarce. Recognising ecosystems as more than just resources for human use is crucial for ensuring militaries do not continue to exploit and devastate the natural world for strategic purposes.

Chapter 7: The Disproportionate Impact of Military-Driven Environmental Damage on Women

7.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the absence of legal recognition of the intersectionality of military-induced environmental problems and gender. This chapter explores the unique vulnerabilities that women experience because of conflict-driven climate change and ecological destruction, and the societal structures that have led to these vulnerabilities. The disproportionate impacts of natural disasters on women will be analysed, using the example of flooding caused by the detonation of the Kakhovka dam. Finally, Nham Tuyet and Johansson's (2001) study will be used to understand the unique effects of herbicidal dioxins on women's reproductive health.

7.2 Legal Recognition of the Intersectionality of Militarism, the Environment and Gender

International Humanitarian Law, the Geneva Conventions and the Additional Protocols provide little protection for both gender and the environment, limiting them to prohibitions against rape and gender discrimination (O'Rourke and Martin, 2023), and widespread, long-term and severe damage to natural environments (Jarose, 2024; O'Rourke and Martin, 2023). The International Committee of the Red Cross created the Gendered Impacts of Armed Conflict report in 2022, which incorporated gender inequality considerations for the military in their protection of civilian obligations (O'Rourke and Martin, 2023). Gender inequality has been linked with sexual and gender-based violence in armed conflict by the UN Security Council's Women, Peace and Security (WPS) agenda, the WPS Secretary-General acknowledges that women and girls are disproportionately affected by environmental problems and global threats (O'Rourke and Martin, 2023). However, these ideas remain underdeveloped and fail to connect the intersectionality of environmental issues, militarism and gender inequality (O'Rourke and Martin, 2023).

7.3 The Unique Vulnerabilities of Conflict-Driven Environmental Degradation Faced by Women

Ecofeminist scholars view war as a “patriarchal institution of domination that values the masculine over the feminine”, which leads to the exploitation of women (Karpenko, Hagenhuber, and Nielsen, 2024: pp.84-99). Wonders and Danner (2015) note that women experience a greater vulnerability to climate change and environmental damage; they emphasise the importance of avoiding further disempowerment of women “by framing them as passive ‘victims’ rather than as active political subjects” (p.405). Predominantly female roles, e.g. childcare and domestic maintenance, are unpaid, leading to many women ending up in poverty: “Women account for 70 per cent of poor people worldwide” (Agostino and Lizarde, 2012: cited in Wonders and Danner, 2015: p.405). Because women are predominantly the household carers, they are usually responsible, particularly in developing countries, for collecting and carrying water, food and fuel. When their environment is destroyed by war, they are forced to travel further for these necessities (Wonders and Danner, 2015; Terry, 2009). The larger the distance and the longer it takes for these women to collect resources, the greater their risk of experiencing male-perpetuated gender-based violence (GBV). This violence tends to be physical or sexual (Wonders and Danner, 2015; Terry, 2009; Sollund et al., 2015). The absence of stable political, economic and security enforcement during conflict and post-conflict environmental degradation increases female exposure to GBV (Fapohunda et al., 2025).

7.4 Women and Conflict-Induced Natural Disasters: The Kakhovka Dam

Women experience different risks and harms than men do in natural disasters and extreme weather events (Wonders and Danner, 2015; Wachholz, 2013). Militarism is intensifying and increasing natural disasters by changing the climate (Kotsis, 2023), conflict events such as the detonation of the Kakhovka dam have created natural disasters like flooding (Van der Vet, 2024). Women represent higher numbers in death rates during and after natural disasters (Wonders and Danner, 2015). Young et al. (1994) argue that women are disadvantaged by their social lives. Although female roles have evolved since Young’s theory was proposed, their ideas remain relevant today, especially in developing countries where women often continue to fulfil traditional household roles. For example, in the event of a flood, women are more likely to be at home with their children, especially if their male partners are away at war. Women are less likely than men to have the strength to or be taught how to climb or swim, childcare would also make them more susceptible to drowning, as protecting a child in a flood would make it more difficult for them to stay afloat and tire them out quickly (Wonders and Danner, 2015; Oxfam, 2005). After a natural disaster, women take on further caretaking responsibilities, often putting

themselves last when it comes to feeding their families, which can lead to malnutrition, particularly when there are food shortages (Wonders and Danner, 2015).

7.5 The Effects of Herbicides on Women's Health: The Second Indochina War

Nham Tuyet and Johansson (2001) investigated the health effects of Agent Orange exposure on Vietnamese women, exploring the link between dioxin contamination and adverse reproductive and hormonal disorders. Women in areas of Indochina which were heavily sprayed with herbicides during the Second Indochina War face direct exposure through air, food and water, as well as indirect exposure through contaminated environments for decades (Nham Tuyet and Johansson, 2001). Women who have been exposed to dioxins report high rates of spontaneous miscarriages, stillbirths, premature births, and severe foetal malformations (Nham Tuyet and Johansson, 2001). Many women have also reported infertility, hormonal imbalances, irregular menstrual cycles, and endometriosis (Nham Tuyet and Johansson, 2001). Women who experience these issues or give birth to disabled children face psychological distress, social stigma and emotional trauma (Nham Tuyet and Johansson, 2001).

7.6 Conclusion

This chapter has explored the critical yet overlooked intersection of militarism, environmental degradation, and gender inequality. It has highlighted the lack of legal recognition of military-induced environmental harm and its gendered consequences, highlighting how existing frameworks fail to address these interconnected issues. The discussion of conflict-driven environmental destruction has underscored the increased vulnerabilities faced by women, particularly in terms of traditional societal structures which form economic dependency, increased caretaking responsibilities and exposure to violence. The case study of the flooding caused by the detonation of the Kakovkha dam has demonstrated how conflict-induced natural disasters disproportionately impact women, intensifying existing social and physical vulnerabilities. Similarly, the long-term health effects of herbicidal warfare reveal the negative reproductive impact on women, worsening gendered inequalities in post-conflict societies.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

8.1 How can criminological frameworks help understand and address environmental harm arising from warfare and its gendered dimensions?

Criminological frameworks address how military states and capitalism are constantly expanding, green criminology explains that these cause environmental harm, which is largely unprotected by international laws. The Treadmill of Production Theory explains how the constant drive for economic and military growth worsens this damage. Ecofeminism and masculinity theories reveal how militarism reinforces gender inequalities, with women facing greater risks due to environmental destruction. These criminological frameworks help expose the systemic causes of war-related ecological harm and its disproportionate impact on women.

8.2 How is the health of the environment neglected during wartime, what are the unintentional and intentional ecological impacts of militarism?

Already weak environmental laws are often ignored during wartime, with monitoring collapsing in war-torn areas. Unintentional impacts include habitat destruction, pollution, unexploded munitions, and nuclear testing, while intentional destruction, such as the detonation of the Kakovkha dam, is used as a military strategy. Despite some temporary ecological benefits from reduced human activity, the long-term damage far outweighs any gains.

8.3 How well do current laws and regulations protect the environment against military activities?

Existing laws like the Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols provide weak protection, as they prioritise human interests over non-human species and ecosystems, they are also difficult to enforce. The high legal threshold for proving environmental war crimes and the lack of strong enforcement mean that militaries rarely face consequences for ecological destruction.

8.4 How are women disproportionately affected by conflict-related environmental harm?

Women suffer further oppression when war destroys local resources, as they are often responsible for collecting food, water and fuel. This increases their exposure to violence and exploitation. Disasters like the Kakhovka dam flooding show how women are more vulnerable during conflict-related environmental crises. Additionally, exposure to toxic chemicals, such as Agent Orange, leads to severe reproductive health issues and long-term economic struggles, reinforcing gender inequality.

8.5 Summary and a Connection of the Findings

An intersectional review was conducted within this dissertation of militarism, environmental harm, and gender inequality using green criminological frameworks. While each chapter focused on specific aspects of this topic, they all connect through key themes: the systemic normalisation of environmental destruction arising from warfare, the limitations of existing legal frameworks in addressing these issues, and the gendered consequences.

Green criminology, ecofeminism and the study of war within criminology provided frameworks to question why domestic crimes and environmental and gendered harms are not treated as criminal during wartime and military preparation activities. They also analysed the continuum of military-industrial expansion. These criminological perspectives link with the findings in Chapters 3, 4, and 5: the indirect environmental harms caused by militarism, the intentional environmental harms caused by militarism, and the gendered impacts of military-induced environmental harms. Combined, these findings show how systemic power structures (i.e. militarism, capitalism, and patriarchy) reinforce each other, resulting in environmental degradation and disproportionate harm to women.

Throughout this dissertation, there has been proof that current laws and treaties fail to effectively regulate military-induced environmental harm. Anthropocentric bias, which does not consider the health of the environment, particularly in times of war, has led to these legal failures. This legal neglect connects with the findings of Chapter 5, where international legal frameworks also fail to consider the intersection of environmental harm and gender.

The findings within this dissertation reflect a pattern that militarism does not affect all people or species equally. Structural inequalities, anthropocentrism, and a lack of accountability prioritise military objectives and state interests over environmental protection and gender equality.

8.6 Contextualising the Findings Considering Existing Literature

The research within this dissertation builds on green criminology, which critiques the exploitation of the environment as a resource for power and control, aligning with the Treadmill of Production Theory (Lynch et al., 2017; Stretsky et al., 2014; Schnaiberg, 1980). Green criminology has helped to understand that legal terms cannot constrict environmental harms, as laws are often insufficient in preventing ecological destruction, as they favour corporate interests.

Ecofeminist and masculinity theories highlight the connection between patriarchal power structures, environmental destruction, and the increased vulnerability of women during and after war. Nham Tuyet and Johansson put the long-term health consequences for women of military-induced environmental harm into context by applying them to the use of herbicides in Indochina.

Previous literature from key scholars such as Wonders and Danner (2015), Lawrence et al. (2015), and Westing (1996) support the idea that militarism exacerbates climate change and creates ecological destruction, particularly for groups who are already marginalised. Studies, like Van der Vet's (2023) research on the detonation of the Kakovkha dam in Ukraine, prove that existing laws do not push for accountability or prevent intentional ecological damage.

8.7 Critical Evaluation of the Methodology

8.7.1 What Worked?

JSTOR, Google Scholar, the UWE Library, and Sage Journals were useful databases which provided plenty of peer-reviewed secondary research for this project. The Finch and Fafinski (2019) method ensured a structured approach to achieve credible and relevant sources and enabled a critical comparison of existing literature. A list of keywords, alternative spellings, and Boolean operators allowed for a refined and precise search. The Open University's PROMPT checklist ensured that data was reliable and relevant to this project. A thematic analysis rounded off the research by effectively identifying key patterns across literature, strengthening the argument on the intersection of militarism, environmental harm, and gender.

8.7.2 Limitations

This project was reliant on secondary data due to ethical, legal and practical restraints. The collection of primary research would have given this project a more in-depth and personal analysis, helping to validate or challenge existing literature. Secondary research may constrain this project by the availability of environmental impact assessments in conflict zones, making it difficult to fully quantify harm. There was a limited amount of existing literature on the intersectionality of gender, environmental harm and militarism, restricting the number of sources used in this project.

8.7.3 Future Improvements

A more in-depth qualitative analysis could be conducted to enhance the credibility of this project by incorporating interviews and case studies with environmental and human rights experts. A comparative analysis of a wider range of case studies with a broader geographical scope would give the project more sustenance. Access to specialised tools and environmental expertise, such as satellite technology and mapping tools to visually and scientifically track changes in the environment caused by warfare, would have provided solid proof and increased the amount of reliable data within this dissertation.

8.8 Applicability: Policy and Practice Recommendations

This project has provided evidence that environmental protections need strengthening in times of war. Ensuring the enforcement of international laws and integrating ecological and gendered considerations into post-conflict recovery strategies are crucial to mitigating negative impacts. A more comprehensive and enforceable approach to environmental conservation during and after conflict is essential to safeguarding the planet's biodiversity and ecological health. Existing legal protections are focused on anthropocentric concerns but rarely consider gender to be a factor; recognition of gender inequality in the context of environmental harm and conflict is necessary. Following Higgins's (2013) suggestions, recognising Ecocide as a crime against peace and reframing environmental destruction as a form of violence could shift global perspectives of environmental harm. Once policies are improved and enforced effectively, states, corporations and militaries should be held accountable for ecological destruction.

8.9 Future Research Directions

An anthropocentric and gender-based study examining the long-term physical health effects on communities affected by war-induced ecological damage. This research would explore how exposure to environmental degradation, such as pollution, toxic waste, and deforestation, physically affects men, women, and gender-diverse individuals differently over time. A comparison of these gendered health outcomes would determine whether biological, social, or economic factors contribute to disparities in physical health. This research would determine how gendered social roles and healthcare access influence vulnerability and recovery in post-conflict environments. This study would provide critical information for public health interventions and gendered policy development.

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